

IODINATION. PART III. STUDIES ON THE IODINATION OF DIFFERENT UNSATURATED ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN THE DARK IN POLAR SOLVENTS.

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Velocity of addition of iodine to β -amylene and phenylacetylene in the dark in polar solvents, *e.g.*, ethyl alcohol and acetic acid, has been investigated. The reaction is termolecular with respect to both iodine and the acceptor. The reaction rate appears to be greater in alcoholic solution than in acetic acid. The temperature coefficient of the reaction rate is not high.

In this part the results of investigations on the velocity of addition of iodine to β -amylene and phenylacetylene in the dark in polar solvents like ethyl alcohol and acetic acid have been described.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The experimental arrangement and a major portion of the experimental procedure have been described in Parts I and II of this series.

Merck's extra pure absolute alcohol was further purified by distillation over metallic calcium before use. Merck's extra pure acetic acid was redistilled before use. B.D.H. phenylacetylene was used after further distillation. Fresh solutions were prepared after every 2 days with freshly distilled β -amylene and phenylacetylene.

The experimental results are recorded in Tables I to V. The velocity of the reaction was found to be proportional to the concentration of the acceptor and to the square of the iodine concentration. The velocity constant was calculated from the equation,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_3(a-x)^2(b-x) \quad \dots (i)$$

where a and b are the initial concentrations of iodine and the acceptor respectively in gram mols per litre and x , the concentration of the iodo product in gram mols per litre in time t (mins.).

From equation (i) by integration we get

$$k_3 = \frac{1}{t(b-a)^2} \left\{ \frac{(b-a)x}{a(a-x)} + \log \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)} \right\} \quad \dots (ii)$$

The relation (ii) was used when $(b-a)$ was considerable. For nearly equimolar mixtures, when $(b-a)$ was very small, the expression (iii) was used.

$$k_3 = \frac{1}{t} \left[\frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{1}{(a-x)^2} - \frac{1}{a^2} \right\} - \frac{b-a}{3} \left(\frac{1}{(a-x)^2} - \frac{1}{a^2} \right) + \dots \right] \quad \dots (iii)$$

The reactions between iodine and β -amylene and iodine and phenylacetylene do not proceed to completion and so the velocity constants were found to decrease with the progress of the reaction. In the earlier stages of the reaction, the amount of di-iodo product formed is negligible. In the following paper the velocity constants are recorded for 10% conversion in the case of β -amylene and 4% in the case of phenylacetylene. For this, graphs were drawn of concentrations of iodine against time and from the graphs times for the respective conversion were found out. This is to ensure the condition that the reverse reaction does not vitiate our results.

R E S U L T S.

Two typical experiments are recorded below.

TABLE I.

Expt. I. Acceptor = β -amylene.				Expt. II. Acceptor = β -amylene.			
Solvent = EtOH.				Solvent = Acetic acid.			
$a = 0.0482M.$		$b = 0.107M.$		$a = 0.046M.$		$b = 0.1M.$	
Temperature = 31° .				Temperature = 31° .			
$t.$	$a-x.$	t (for 10% conversion).	$k_3.$	$t.$	$a-x.$	t (for 10% conversion).	$k_3.$
0	0.0482			0	0.0460		
5	0.0444	7.25 min.	4.4	20	0.0425	31.0 min.	1.2
15	0.0412			40	0.0407		
30	0.0390						

Similar calculations were made in all the experiments and the results are summarised in Tables II to V.

Effect of varying the Concentrations of the Reactants.

TABLE II.

Acceptor = β -amylene. Temperature = 31° .					
a.	b.	k_3	a.	b.	k_3
	Ethyl alcohol.			Ethyl alcohol.	
0.05M	0.214M	4.0	0.075	0.082	4.5
0.05	0.107	4.4	0.025	0.0268	4.7
0.0482	0.107	4.4		Acetic acid.	
0.0375	"	4.0	0.03	0.1	1.1
0.0125	"	4.3	"	0.075	1.0
0.075	0.0535	4.9	"	0.05	1.0
0.05	"	3.7	0.046	0.1	1.2
0.025	"	4.0	0.0466	0.05	1.1
			0.025	0.025	1.2

TABLE III.

Acceptor = Phenylacetylene. Temp = 21.5°. Solvent = Ethyl alcohol.

a.	b.	$k_3 \times 10^2$.	a.	b.	$k_3 \times 10^2$.
0.0625M	0.111M	11.3	0.0461	0.0167M	11.2
0.0461	"	11.2	0.0234	"	11.5
0.0300	"	11.3	0.0300	0.055	10.5
0.0234	"	10.3	0.0234	"	11.0

Effect of Temperature.

TABLE IV.

Acceptor = β -amylene.

Solvent.	θ .	a.	b.	k_3 .	v.
Ethyl alcohol	31.0	0.025M	0.0535M	4.0	
"	6.0	"	"	0.8	1.90
"	31.0	0.05	0.107	4.4	
"	6.0	"	"	0.8	1.98
Acetic acid	31.0	0.03	0.1	1.1	
"	11.0	"	"	0.6	1.35

v = temperature coefficient for 10° rise

$$= \left(\frac{k_{31}}{k_6} \right)^{\frac{10}{\theta}}$$

in the case of ethyl alcohol as solvent

$$= \left(\frac{k_{31}}{k_{11}} \right)^{\frac{10}{\theta}}$$

in the case of acetic acid as solvent.

TABLE V.

Acceptor = Phenylacetylene. Solvent = Ethyl alcohol.

θ	a.	b.	$k_3 \times 10^2 = k$.	v.
21.5	0.046M	0.167M	11.2	
11.5	"	"	6.1	1.84

$$v = \text{the temperature coefficient for } 10^\circ = \left(\frac{k_{21.5}}{k_{11.5}} \right)$$

DISCUSSION.

The reactions have the following characteristics :—

1. The reaction velocity is proportional to the concentration of the acceptor and to the square of the concentration of iodine, *i.e.*, the reaction is termolecular with respect to both.

2. The temperature coefficient for a 10° rise is not high being less than 2.0. It is greater in alcoholic solutions than in acetic acid.

3. The rate of the reaction is greater in alcoholic solution than in acetic acid.

The following mechanism will explain the observed facts.

We may assume according to the observations made by Loeb (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 53, 805) that in polar solvents like alcohol and acetic acid, iodine molecules exist as I_4 .

The reaction may be represented by the equation,

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= k_2[A][I_4] - k'[AI_2][I_2] \\ &= k_2[A][I_2]^2 - k'[AI_2][I_2] \\ &= k_2(b-x)(a-x)^2 - k'x(a-x) \\ &= k_2(a-x)^2(b-x) - k'(a-x)x. \end{aligned}$$

In the initial stages of the reaction when x is very small

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_2(a-x)^2(b-x) \quad \dots (i)$$

where a and b are the initial concentrations of iodine and the acceptor respectively and x , the concentration of the iodo product at any time t .

The equation (i) has been found to hold good very satisfactorily. The increase in velocity of reaction for a 10° rise in temperature is of the order of 1.8 which is very much greater than the values observed in non-polar solvents. This in itself lends support to the view that the mechanisms of the reaction in the two types of solvents are different.

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